

THE FOURTH REICH

EUROPE - TOTALITARIAN OR DEMOCRATIC ?

IMPORTANT :- This is a long document with many new and valuable concepts. My advice is therefore to read it only when you have the time and energy to embrace the contents; and then maybe in parts. Then read it all again after reflection on it.

This paper examines the wide range of topics which centre around the freedom of people to choose the way they are governed and the way their leaders spend tax payers hard earned cash, sometimes without consent of the voters. This discusses those subjects of importance to the electorate, who have handed their power to the few who seek to govern them. But it also points out that politicians forget that they are supposed to represent the people and as a result spend the wealth which does not belong to them on subjects they were not elected to get involved in.

We also look to see how the ancient teaching of karma (as you sow so shall you reap) has impacted on entrenched thinking over the centuries. Thinking is the main factor in human decision making and action.

Few people look to discover the true source of their thinking.

CONTENTS

Section	Page
Introduction	2
Liberation from Cultural Conditioning	2
Some History of Europe and Control	3
The Psychology of War	7
The Psychology of the Fourth Reich	8
The Common Market is Born	12
Germany and France Try to Make Friends	14
The Concept of the European Union	15
Does Modern Democracy Work?	16
The Birth of the European Union	22
Areas of European Control and Controversy	24
The Euro Currency Failure	26
The Idea of a European Army	29
Conclusions	32
Appendix 1 - Eurocentricism	34

INTRODUCTION

The question has arisen as to the way the European Union is mutating. What began as a simple agreement for several countries to trade with each other in a more relaxed way, has become a faceless bureaucratic control of more than two dozen countries; all with widely diverse cultures. So it is now necessary to examine, with doctorate scholarship, the way Europe has become controlled in this first quarter of the 21st century. First let me define my terms of reference here in relation to this paper, so that all are clear what the tone of this paper is about.

Doctorate scholarship :- An approach to the study and research of human relationships and affairs which looks honestly at the facts and attempts to see the truth (sometimes hidden) which is behind them. Also the mode of study does not use either political or religious leanings to influence the outcome or the conclusion resulting from the study. Impartiality in as best a way as possible. It also should contain well articulated critical thinking.

Totalitarianism - A mode of government that is systematised and dictatorial and requires complete subservience to state controls.

Democracy - A system of government by the whole population or by eligible members of a state. Normally controlled and decided by elected members of that state, elected by the people they are to serve.

Of course we should understand that there are many degrees of these things and one mode can borrow parts from another and still retain the name of its basic system of government.

Liberation from Cultural Conditioning

What is really necessary is for the people of the West, as individuals; and those who follow western ways; to become liberated from the prison of thinking which has dominated the way the world is being shaped. Another name for this is cultural conditioning; (it also relates to the mystical subject of karma¹). It is an almost impossible task to be free of such conditioning, and if I am honest here, it will take each individual most of a lifetime to become so liberated from the ideas imbibed in the childhood years and born into the thinking of

¹ Karma - the doctrine from the ancient Vedanta philosophy, which recognises the rebirth of the human soul and the debt or habit of previous actions being carried forward into its new embodiment.

each person. The thinking which shapes the lives of each individual is embedded into their psychology as young babies. Coming even while the child is in the womb (karma). This is added to throughout childhood and school years from parents, teachers and other associates. These thoughts and the education given are all based on a model which has been established maybe for centuries. This happens in such a way that is very subtle and becomes the very basis of thought and action of each individual, such that we will all say, "This is what I am." This very feeling and statement are not absolutely true. Yet it is such conditioning which is controlling Europe.

However, to become truly liberated from this entrenched conditioning takes a willpower which the average individual does not have. Also the effort to become liberated from this conditioning needs to be sustained for many decades of a person's life. Such a determination is not within the capacity of the average person. Hence I have conceived this paper to give assistance to those readers who truly wish their spirit to be free and to be able to honestly think for themselves about the way the world is currently being governed by its leaders.

Another way to begin this process is to travel and spend some time in the countries which have very a different culture from that which we knew as children. Not simply a holiday visit but research which would entail many discussions with the people of those other countries, so as to discover differences in the ways of thinking. This will give rise to many questions about the culture of one's own country or way of life and a fresh view of it; and a chance to see the power of conditioned thought.

Therefore the spirit of this paper carries with it no obligation to adopt any matter which is presented here; unless the reader has cross checked for themselves whatever is written. This paper is not an attempt to present a new way of seeing the world, but of opening the possibility that readers may decide to do that for themselves.

Some History of Europe and Control

Before reading this paper it is a pre-condition to have read the section called 'Eurocentricism' in my paper called "Did Jesus Study Vedanta". No need to read the whole paper - only the part at the beginning. For this purpose I have reproduced it as Appendix One to

this paper. The concept of karma (see footnote above) came from Vedanta and was once part of Christian doctrine before it was made into a heresy; for the convenience of one Roman Emperor.

Having read that appendix readers should be in the position of beginning to see that there may be another way to view the world, other than the one which has been shoe-horned into the thinking of most nations in the world through the agency of European colonialism.

It is necessary to appreciate that it is this psychology of Eurocentricism which is at the heart of how the controls of the European Union have gradually mutated. Those few nations who started the concept off, France, Germany, Belgium, Italy, Luxembourg and the Netherlands, were still under the psychology of the Third Reich of Hitler when they conceived the idea of a common trading market. This third Reich concept was to politically (with military might) dominate all the countries which bordered Germany; and of course to include Germany itself. But the way Hitler chose to do it was one of the world's greatest abominations ever carried out in human history; demonstrating that people who call themselves "Christian" had not given up the practice of killing or burning at the stake those who they did not agree with (after all -- killing someone on a cross, who was thought to be disagreeable, is the basis of the Christian ideas). There is so much talk and remembrance of the millions of people of a different religion to Hitler killed by his regime, yet there is not so much remembrance of the millions of Christians killed (or burned alive) in previous centuries by their own so called European Christian leaders.

So let us recall here what the European Christians did to their own followers in the name of "control". If any person did not agree with the doctrine of the official Church, they would be termed 'heretic'. Under the regime of the Inquisition Courts they would have no public fair trial, could not get a defence lawyer (such lawyers were also likely to be called heretic) and not only the accused but also any witnesses would be tortured until convicting words were spoken. The term "third degree" comes from the last and often fatal system of torture used by the Inquisition. Finally, if still alive, the accused would be certainly found guilty and burned at the stake. This same regime was applied to millions of women (called witches) who held the natural

herbal cure tradition handed down from before the Christian era. These ladies were termed heretic mainly because they knew how to use herbs to prevent pregnancy or to terminate one. The result was that the Christians destroyed the herbal medicine tradition of Europe, resulting in several centuries of plagues, which killed many millions more people.

We should note here that herbal or Nature's cures are inexpensive and boost or assist the human immune system to fight (and win) any disease, remaining efficacious for all time. Their modern replacement is highly expensive, harms the immune system, poisons the human body (side effects) and the pathogens are able to mutate and render the medicine ineffective. What a "wonderful" health legacy the European Christians have given to the European people. Yet this Christian atrocity is all forgotten and the religious atrocity of Hitler is regularly remembered.

Because the Germans are good at record keeping there are records of hundreds of thousands of names of women executed as above. Many villages only had one or two women remaining. This happened in all countries controlled by the Holy Roman Empire (HRE), totalling many millions. This is how barbaric the Europeans had remained after pro-claiming to be Christian for more than a thousand years. The Inquisition courts were finally abandoned (or renamed) only one hundred years ago. But don't think the Christians aren't able to revive their ways. Remember what Hitler did to the Jewish people. This same thing many totalitarian regimes are enacting in this 21st century around the world. We must not let the EU mutate to become totalitarian; but it is run by Christians and they still have such tendencies embedded within their psychology; showing that they did not hear the words of the man they claim to follow. Such is the power of karma.

Yet the memory of that earlier Christian atrocity (the Inquisition) is retained deeply within the souls of all Europeans (karma). Hence all the countries under the threat of Hitler's third Reich idea naturally rose up to fight back. This eventually included Britain, only because of a treaty between Britain and Poland; showing that the English statement "my word is my bond" still held true. Britain was not threatened by Hitler at the beginning of the Third Reich implementation.

So how did Europe get to the threat of a third Reich? you may ask, and what were the first and second Reichs?

The First Reich was not called that as such. It was the domination of Europe by the Roman Catholic church called the Holy Roman Empire (HRE); the regime initially responsible for the previous holocaust mentioned above, of burning millions of fellow Christians. The HRE was the attempt by the Romans to continue their domination of Europe after the failed military method became too expensive and cumbersome. Domination through thought and religious ideas was seen to be a cheaper method of control, and both more lucrative and effective. The HRE went on for at least one thousand years and began to decline in the nineteenth century of the modern era. Not so long ago.

The Germanic peoples were a very fanatic and dominant force within the HRE. I call them Germanic because the nation now called Germany was not formed before the Second Reich. This became what was later called the German Empire. The Germanic peoples were previously a bunch of isolated kingdoms spreading out from the lowlands near the north sea towards the high country of Austria. This Second Reich brought under one political control all the lands which bordered onto Denmark, Russia, Austria, Belgium, the Netherlands and France. Hence the German nation was formed.

Having become established as a nation the will to dominate did not leave them. Hence Hitler was given the consent of the people through a sort of 'democratic' process, to spread the German Empire into the lands which bordered the country known then as Germany. This is how Hitler's regime came to be call the Third Reich.

The above is a potted history relevant to the subject of this paper.

We must not forget that Europeans (Christians) like to eliminate their dissenters in one way or another; usually by killing them. Here the term 'Europeans' includes the peoples of the USA and other ex-colonials.

The Psychology of War

The opening of the above first section points out how difficult it is for human beings to control or remove entrenched thinking patterns. The mechanism for this is called 'karma' in Sanskrit. Generally Europeans have little knowledge of this subject or how it works. Those habits or traits established in a person's life create impressions which form seeds. These wrap around the soul and are planted into the mental garden of the newly conceived child which the soul moves into at death of its previous body². These slowly germinate as circumstances decide, to form habits or tendencies similar to those held in the previous embodiment. These habits are sometimes difficult to control. Any parent who has closely observed their children growing up will have seen this happen; but may not have been able to understand it in the way as described above; due to European ignorance of karma. The mention here of 'karma' clarifies what I meant above when I wrote, "retained deeply within the souls." Such a deep memory governs the way people behave. Most of us have very little control over how we think and behave where karma is involved.

This deep memory happens with many subjects and more so with the matters connected with war between nations. I remember in the mid 1950's sitting around a lunch table at my grandmother's house with my mother, grandmother and aunt all remembering episodes of ducking and diving from the bombs dropping on London; and all the other things which the destruction of the second world war had brought into their lives. All three of them spoke as if those things had happened the week before; yet it was more than a decade after the war had ended. Such is the deep impression that war leaves on the human memory.

This same thing happens with greater intensity for those who were the perpetrators of the death and destruction. When it was decided that the first world war would stop at eleven o'clock on the eleventh of November in 1918, it brought a sudden need to stop the psychology of war in the commanders and the troops. But they could not do it. In the morning of the eleventh of November that year the commanders, whose whole career was war mongering, could not stop sending their troops out to try and kill as many of the enemy as possible in those last

² Anyone who doubts this needs to investigate how they came to be living in their current body.

official hours of that war. Many thousands of lives were lost on that day which need not have been taken; some only minutes before the fighting was due to officially stop at eleven o'clock. All because military men cannot control the habitual thinking of their own psychology; it is this same way that cultural conditioning works and is no different to the psychology mentioned above in connection with Christian atrocities.

Here I hope I have underlined the strength of entrenched habit. Understanding it is key to understanding this paper.

This same thing happened across the nations of Europe who had been involved in the second world war. They were all suffering from the entrenched psychology of the Third Reich. Those nations which had been resisting the ideas of the Third Reich could not stop thinking of how all those same nations could be under one control in some way or another. This came out as the idea that European peoples should never smash up each others cities and kill their people ever again. Slowly Europeans are learning to be less barbaric. But it is really still the psychology of the Third Reich in the form of, "Let's all get together under one control". They could not stop thinking along the lines of the Third Reich; yet it appeared to be against such thinking. Human beings are really puppets of their own entrenched thinking even though they believe they are free. This is why I opened with the theme 'liberation'.

Perhaps now my readers will start to look inwardly at their own cultural conditioning. If we do not eliminate the individual's European tendency towards controlling others (leading to barbarism), then we can never eliminate it from communities and nations as a whole. Look at the manner in which the EU politicians control the Brexit debate. They have clearly made a prisoner of each member state. Getting in is relatively easy - getting out is very difficult.

The Psychology of the Fourth Reich

After the failure of the Third Reich idea the German peoples still had the idea of becoming one with all those other countries by way of looking for forgiveness for the terrible damage that their military forces had carried out within the lands and cities of those involved in that war.

On a school holiday to Germany when I was fifteen years old (1959), I met Güdrün, a very nice German girl with whom I later exchanged letters. We say it was teenagers having an experience of 'love at first sight'. After some years of learning each other's language, visits to each other and many letters, we were planning to get married. I remember clearly, within the German friends and family groups of Güdrün, the discussions about this intention of ours. How much it would show people of both nations that the English and the Germans were prepared to be reconciled after that terrible war (about twenty years prior). I did then and I do now applaud this attitude. This showed me how much the German nation was seeking to become joined up to those whom they had previously sought to conquer. Yet the habit of wishing to conquer had not left the German nation entirely. There was in those days a movement aimed at the reunification of East and West Germany.

In the aftermath of the war several nations decided to take control of the affairs of Germany - especially those affairs of a military nature. Hence the Russians had taken control of what became known as East Germany. Those Germans in West Germany wanted their whole nation to be one. This desire was a continuation of the psychology of conquest or their national control, in some way or another. The psychology of the Third Reich was being slowly reborn as the desire or need to get their nation back under their own control; the Fourth Reich maybe? We may think we have eliminated the perpetrators of the Third Reich. But let's not be fooled that their souls and their karma will not come back to haunt us all, and arise in a slightly different form. Each Reich is not a carbon copy of the previous one. But control is at its heart.

And those readers who cannot embrace the concept of the soul's rebirth need to work on the first exercise mentioned above, that of cultural conditioning. For nearly five hundred years after the times of Jesus, the Christians of Europe understood and knew about the reincarnation of the human soul. It was Christian teaching. But one Roman emperor decided it did not suit him and had the doctrine made into a heresy. Since then (for 1,500 years) the cultural conditioning has made Europeans disbelieve any notion of there being more than one embodiment of the human soul. Karma goes hand in hand with

rebirth of the soul. So here is one aspect of cultural conditioning which needs to be removed so as to fully comprehend this paper.

Given the atrocious acts perpetrated by the Nazis in Europe during the second world war, no civilised person would condone such things. These were fully documented with pictures etc. so it cannot be denied that it happened. How therefore can anyone explain the subsequent rise of Neo-Nazi groups in more than a dozen European countries between the end of that war and the end of the 20th century? The only way it can be truly understood is that the karma of previous Nazi types has been reborn into the next embodiment of their souls during the decades after the war. I think no one can find a more plausible explanation; and also to see the power of karma on us all.

Although many post war Germans (not all as we now know) were opposed to the regime of Hitler, this did not mean that the German nation had deserted its psychology of wanting things their own way in Europe. Doubts about their own psychology in this respect were described by German politicians in a February 2019 interview on the British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC) radio. They were concerned about totalitarian tendencies in the current policies of the EU. The phrase "Sleep-walking into totalitarianism." was mentioned.

The president of the European Union said in February 2019, *"I've been wondering what that special place in hell looks like for those who promote Brexit without even a sketch of a plan to carry it out safely."* This relates to the Christian's religious concept of what happens to the souls of transgressors against their doctrine (i.e. hell). It is therefore clearly a comment motivated by religious concepts, it is not political dialogue. This is the language of the First Reich, the Holy Roman Empire, where heretics against Christian doctrine were burned at the stake or otherwise threatened with 'hell'. It shows that the psychology of the First Reich is not dead after all these centuries. What the president of the EU has said is a religious attack on innocent UK politicians, condemning them, in his opinion, to hell, because they simply wish to carry out the democratic wishes of the British people. The same thing was done to innocent Christians who wanted to think for themselves. Is the EU sleepwalking towards the Fourth Reich? We must start to learn how karma works – life to life.

What do we mean by "sleepwalking"? It is a phenomenon whereby a person gets out of bed in the night time but does not wake up. Their appearance and actions are all those of a person who is apparently awake and acting with reason. But they are not conscious of what they are doing and are hence not taken to be fully responsible for their actions. This clearly describes European politicians driven by karma.

An example of this we can say is now known by most people in the world. Near the end of the last century some clever computer technicians in the UK developed a way to use telephone lines to send messages encoded by computer software. Long messages could be sent quicker and cheaper than a normal telephone calls; also the recipient did not have to be at home when the message was received by their own computer. This we now know as email. It seemed to be a harmless way of people communicating with each other. Those technicians could be said to have sleepwalked into opening a world wide Pandora's box.

One of the originators of the world-wide-web idea has recently confessed that he did not know then what a damaging thing he had invented. Their intentions were no doubt good and noble, and being that kind of people they did not build criminal psychology into the system they unleashed onto the world. Hence when criminals put a little thought into the potential of email, they soon became capable of getting into the private lives of all those who used email; resulting in thefts of personal data, money and other private matters. Good intentions mutated into disastrous results. The Silicon Valley technicians have admitted in February 2019 that they were negligent (i.e. asleep) in not looking at the darker possibilities of connecting the world electronically. It is notable that all the leaders of high tech Silicon Valley companies do not allow their children to have smart phones or a connection with any other form of global electronic communications. What do they know?

Until each individual who connects to the world-wide-web needs to fully identify themselves with a licence number and other forms of identification, then the spiders in that web will continue to do mischief. The whole idea of freedom of access to the web is a misconception.

The same thing which happened with email has happened with the internet; except the Pandora's box is a thousand times more devastating. Criminals, abusers, thieves etc. do not now need to leave their desks, let alone their city or country, to carry out crimes against countries, companies, governments and individuals. The world has been sleepwalked into a highly destructive system of communication all in the name of a little convenience. No one knows now how to stop the damage to people's lives which has occurred as a result. Governments seem to be powerless. We all lived much more safely before the internet and then we all obtained our food, clothing and shelter without it.

Is Silicon Valley responsible for the rape of the world and the abuse of its children? the theft of the world's bank accounts? stealing the world's secret military information? obtaining the world's personal and private information? and many other things done at great distance which could never have happened if Silicon Valley had not opened the Pandora's box? Now governments are afraid of regulating it. Why?

No doubt the six nations who started the idea of the Common Market all had good intentions. But were they all sleepwalking towards a European control system which veers towards totalitarianism? It has clearly now got out of control, just like the internet. What can they do? The answer is the same as for the Christian church's current sexual abuse scandal. Nothing. The organisation is too large for the Pope, the Archbishop of Canterbury or any other leader to effect any control. The EU is now such a huge unwieldy organisation that nothing can be done to make it work in the harmless way it was originally intended.

The Common Market is Born

The first idea of getting together to prevent further conflict between nations was in 1951 between France and West Germany relating to collaboration in the production of steel. This had behind it a peaceful way to begin the rebuilding of European countries after the devastation of the war. It was called the Treaty of Paris. France, the Netherlands, Belgium, West Germany, Luxembourg and Italy all worked together on producing that treaty. This treaty had an unfixed expiry date attached to it. Presumably because they guessed that eventually those countries would be rebuilt at some time in the future.

It is interesting to note here that both Germany and Britain were leaders in both engineering and steel production. Yet Britain was not included in the Treaty of Paris. "Why?" you may ask. There may have been many subsidiary reasons, but the main one was that the term "Europe" did not automatically include the UK at that time. The memory of people is appallingly short and we all easily superimpose our current thinking onto ideas and publications of the past. The idea that the UK is not part of Europe would seem absurd today. In the 1940's and 1950's it was not such an absurd idea; simply because the UK had a world-wide Empire. The largest the world has ever known in recorded history. Britain had no need to think of itself as being joined to all those countries who had been contenders for world colonisation in the many previous centuries of Eurocentricism. Hence both Britain and those European countries who worked on the Treaty of Paris would not think that the UK should be included. This psychology continued into the few years that followed, when those same six countries carried on meeting and talking about further ways in which they could work together.

The growing wave of collaboration between those six countries eventually produced two further agreements. The European Defence Community and The European Political Community; further ways of working together to avoid conflict and to pool their resources. Once again we should realise that the term "European" did not include Britain. Both these two new agreements had behind them the idea of creating a "United States of Europe"; although initially this did not include Britain, it had as its ambition to extend the number of nations far outside the original six (France, The Netherlands, Belgium, West Germany, Luxembourg and Italy). It is interesting to note here that all those nations which were envisaged as becoming the United States of Europe, were predominantly (if not entirely) Christian. i.e. this means that it was related to the Holy Roman Empire or the First Reich mentioned above. Once again showing that established psychologies do not die easily.

So we can see how easily the idea of a European Economic Community (EEC) arose within those six nations. This idea was simply to create a situation where those six members could trade with each other and not have the need for customs checks at their respective borders.

This was formed in the Treaty of Rome agreed and signed by the six in 1957. It is easy to understand how countries whose land borders butt onto each other would wish to eliminate the need to make checks of the movement of their produce at those borders. Where there are hundreds of kilometres of land along which to enact controls it can become an almost impossible task to prevent the smuggling of taxable products across those borders. Hence it makes sense to remove the need for levying taxes at the borders. Especially since this only creates counter levies by the other nation and nobody wins in the end. This subject did not affect the UK in the same way, where, due to being an island (or group of islands) its borders have remained the same for millennia as against only centuries for some European countries. Also it is not so easy to walk across the borders where the sea separates one country from another.

The EEC was mainly about trade. It did not include the depth of control of so many cultural ways of doing things which were introduced later. The original idea of the EEC eventually mutated to become the European Union in 1993. The next step towards greater control.

Germany and France Try to Make Friends

The situation of Europe after the second world war gradually lead to the realisation that Russia had ambitions similar to those of Hitler. This caused the leaders of Germany and France to make an agreement to prevent the possibility of any further conflict between themselves and to eliminate, as far as possible, any future chance of such conflict. This lead eventually to the signing of the Élysée Treaty in September 1963. This was opposed by both the UK and the USA, since the treaty contained elements of defence (i.e. potentially military matters).

We need to ask, "Why did France and West Germany need to make another agreement, and one containing a military element, so soon after the six nations behind the EEC had signed up to the Common Market?"

The answer lies within the psychology of the French President, General de Gaulle. He saw both the Russians and the United States of America as obstacles to his hopes of forming a United States of Europe. He was a military man, with all the military psychology spoken of above. Hence he wanted to win his own private battles with other

nations. Albeit these were now economic battles not military ones. He did not wish interference from Russia, the USA or Britain, who he saw as being, perhaps incorrectly, a puppet nation of the USA. The Élysée Treaty did not mention other trade agreements, the USA, Britain or the North Atlantic Treaty Organisation (NATO). This alarmed both the UK and the USA leaders.

Eventually president John F. Kennedy of the USA put pressure on the German politicians to include in the Treaty, co-operation with the USA and to consider including the UK into the EEC. This last point President de Gaulle was definitely opposed to. Overall de Gaulle was thoroughly disappointed with the Germans giving in to the USA. Hence the original purpose of the Élysée Treaty was mainly thwarted; leaving France somewhat isolated. This resulted in the UK's first two attempts to join the EEC (1963 & 1967) being vetoed by President de Gaulle.

The Concept of the European Union

Britain eventually joined the EEC in 1973 after four years of negotiations. This was only possible after de Gaulle had resigned in 1969. When Britain joined the EEC it was joining a free-trade group of nations. British law and British sovereignty were not seen to be under threat at that time. This would have been the same for all other EEC members at their time of joining the group; because the law behind European Court of Justice did not specifically over-ride national law; it was created to ensure compliance with the terms of the Treaty of Rome. But law as such is not a static thing. It is interpretation which finally holds the key.

No nation will ever wish to be seen to make one legal decision at one time and later when the same circumstances arise to then make a different decision in law. Thus the subject of "case law" raises its controlling head; and when the same issue is raised as in a previous case - there becomes little need for a judgement other than to point to the "case law". This often means that matters or situations not originally envisaged within the wording of a specific law will mutate according to circum-stances. One minor case in Italy in 1964 resulted in a judgement which stated that EEC law takes precedent over national law. This one case re-wrote the European Court of Justice rules and hence the law governing matters throughout the European

club. Case law is a veritable mine-field. Thus we have the roots and causes behind the mutation of the good intentions of people. More possibilities for control.

Does Modern Democracy Work?

The way the EU is organised is along democratic lines. This means that somehow decisions have to be made by elected politicians for the benefit of all member countries in the EU club.

Here we take the term 'democracy' to mean a method of getting a sensible government to organise the affairs of the people which it represents. But the last part of the 20th century and all of this century democracy has become more a game of statistics than one of care for the people it is supposed to serve.

In a democratic country the power is supposed to be in the hands of the people who decide which regime they wish to serve them and run their country for them. Yet in the UK for many decades since the second world war government has been more a battle between two parties than a concerted attempt to run a country efficiently. Hence the cost in time of reorganising the country to suit one political idea was thrown away when a different party became elected and spent the first two or three years of office undoing the work of the previous government using tax payers (voters) money. Is this what the people expected democracy to be? Yes or no, it still means that governing the people and the country is inefficient due to the time and money wasted on party politics.

One of the two UK parties basically arose from and represented the average working person - the labourer; from which word it took its name; the Labour Party. The second was the party which was originally formed by the more privileged class of people, those who owned or ran businesses of one kind or another; called the Conservative Party. The time and talk taken up by these politicians was more to do with running down the other party than the business of running the country. They seemed to forget that the power they had in their position in parliament was given to them when voters gave up their power on the ballot paper.

This is the point here, democracy really is the handing over of the individual power to chose, to an elected person who then carries that

accumulated power of his/her voters into the position of government. But when the political game becomes a matter of statistics then the media becomes involved in both influencing the voters and predicting the election result weeks before; all this so as to manipulate the statistics into a desired direction one way or another. The average person knows little of the real matters of government hence many can be easily influenced by material which is broadcast in newspapers, radio and television. There have been clear situations in the UK where a particular newspaper decision to undermine one political party caused a collapse of that party's voting statistics; simply playing on the gullibility of the public when they read sensational material in a newspaper. Is that democracy? It becomes the choice of the media not the choice of the people. Some countries have recognised this and have banned campaigning and media involvement in their elections, days or weeks prior to the date of the election; so as to give true democracy a chance.

The ignorance of the voters is a factor here. We need lessons and proof that we can drive a car. Immigrants need now to pass a tricky test to get permission to stay in the UK. Yet no one needs training or proof of competency to vote for their leaders. Have we missed something here?

Later in the 20th century when the desire to get into power in government became greater than the desire to serve the people, the parties began to desert their traditional aims so as to appeal to a greater number of voters. Hence, for example, the manifesto of the 'New Labour' movement looked very similar to that of the Conservative party manifesto. It was this 'look alike' situation of the Conservative Party and the Labour Party which added to the rise of other smaller parties who wanted to offer non-traditional subjects to the electorate. Hence the total vote became fragmented and people's votes were wasted on parties which would never have any chance of being in power in government, as they mainly put forward fewer issues. Is this what the basis of democracy is all about, people's votes virtually being flushed down the drain?

In many European countries there are multiple parties standing for election. Rendering the votes of millions of people valueless. For example the 2008 Italian general election had 31 different parties

seeking votes. Nearly six million votes for minority parties did not contribute to electing the parties which finally made up the governing coalition. More than half of those votes (for 23 minor parties) resulted in no seats being gained. These votes could have changed the final elected coalition for another one. This is why I called it "flushed down the drain". Is this what the concept of democracy is really for? We may say that this choice is for the people, but I say that we need to include the subject of government and its statistics in junior schools so that children over seven years begin to understand how democracy works, with some of the above facts included. Such education should clearly not include matters of party politics; but could result in a licence to vote at elections.

This raises another important question. Does the election of a government need to include the matter of party politics? In the oldest democracy of the world in modern history, the City of London, there are no party politics. The "Square Mile" as it is known, has 25 wards or sections. One hundred councillors are elected to serve those wards - on the basis of their individual talents and specialities; not in any way based on any party political leanings. This single square mile handles more revenue and has a higher density of financial, accounting and legal companies than any other square mile on this planet. Its government of that square mile cannot be equalled in quality and efficiency anywhere else in the world. Council meetings are all about matters of governing the square mile (and its many other areas of the UK for which it is responsible). No time is spent on arguing about party political matters or having to influence votes of opposing parties; because there are none.

During the earlier part of the 20th Century many local authority governments (counties and borough councils) in the UK used exactly this City model. Later when party politics saw that local authority elections were a way of influencing general elections, they began to campaign in local authority elections. This has led to the same kind of inefficiency in local affairs when a newly elected party seeks to undo matters of a previous local administration. This uses large sums of the voters taxes. Then the new local administration seeks to implement new ways of doing things with the illusion that they will always be in power. The same scenario occurs when another party

takes over power. This is not what voters expect of democracy and is inefficient in time and resources; and means their money is spent badly without their consent.

The worst part about this is that local government areas in the UK are now listed with party political labels. This means that when a party in central government is not the same one in control of a local government area, the central government subtly withholds funding for important matters in those local government areas. This is with an attempt to sway the voters decisions in a general election. This is not democracy working well. It is divisive and simply lust for power not the will to serve those people who elected them.

It is interesting to note that the origin of the UK's current 'House of Commons' originated in the 13th century when local authority representatives came to London to meet and discuss matters of importance in running and taxing the country as a whole and for their own local areas. The House of Commons did not arise until the early 14th century when those who met from the 'shires' had a separate meeting from those of the nobility. At that time the country was governed without party politics.

So government can exist without party politics where all those elected will have equal voice in the decision making. Also they will be free to vote in government on any issue raised, based on its merits, not based on party policy or pressure from party leaders. Where party politics controls the voting statistics it is not really democratic if an elected member cannot decide to vote against an issue based on his/her own belief and understanding.

Another strange facet of modern multi-party politics, within the democracy idea, is that a government can take control of a country with only a small proportion of voters who voted for the party which takes control. For example in the 1992 UK general election 78% of the electorate voted; with the winning party getting 42% of the vote. This means the people accepted that they were to be governed by a party which had less than one third of the electorate behind their position of power. ($0.78 \times 0.42 = 0.328$) The proportion of 78% was the highest turnout in the UK for 18 years. Which means that in many previous elections there may have been less than one third of voters behind the

ruling party. This is an obvious area of potential unrest amongst the electorate.

This showed itself after the UK referendum on EU membership in 2016. Only 52% voted to leave and those who were part of the 48% who wished to remain have been claiming ever since that the UK should not recognise the small percentage difference and should hold another referendum. Here it seems the 'remainers' failed to see that the 52% on a voter turn out of 72% gave a higher percentage of UK citizens for Brexit than the 1992 general election result for the Conservative party to run the country. The UK electorate did not ask for another general election as a result of 32% of the voters backing an elected government in 1992; so why should it change tactics and ask for another referendum based on 37% (i.e. 0.52×0.72) of the UK voters agreeing to leave the EU.

Riding on the back of the above multi-party phenomenon is the hung parliament syndrome or coalition. This has its worst implications when, for example, a basically leftish party gains 42% of the seats in parliament and a right-wing party gains 38% of the seats. But a centre ground party gets 15% of the seats or less. If the leftish party takes power they would only be able to govern the country if they were to get agreement from the centre ground party on any particular issue. Even if they agree to a coalition it would not be much different. Hence a party with possibly 15% or less of the voters behind them would have a large part of the control of the country. Is this really democracy?

Those seeking election under a democratic regime usually put in their manifesto such items as; health; education; housing; food & farming; employment etc. Such things which fulfil the three basic needs of all humans - viz. food, clothing and shelter. But such things as space exploration and particle physics do not appear in the pre-election material. Why? Simply because such things are not a basic necessity of human existence, and the electorate would not be so interested. Yet modern governments spend thousands of millions of pounds (or dollars) on the useless matters connected with space, interstellar and solar system investigations.

All this because they are chasing an American dream created by Hollywood, that human kind, in large numbers, is able to travel with

great ease across the galaxy. This is a very expensive dream. We must wake up and see that such travel is 100% an illusion. Do politicians seek the permission of their electorate to spend so much money on these matters, when such real things, here on this planet, as employment, housing and health have not been solved? The answer is no! The huge sums of money spent by democratically elected governments on the useless matters of space and particle physics, would solve many problems here on the ground. But it seems the electorate do not have any say in it. Another failure of democracy.

Due to having the worst examples of all evils on this planet, the USA has many serious social and existential problems within its own borders. The huge wealth wasted on space exploration etc. should have been used to put their own house in order. Is that use of American tax payers money democratic? It is rightly called "the American dream". Lets not allow Europe to follow suit.

Hence we can say that, although the concept of democracy is a good one, there is a question of how valid the current model is due to the way it has mutated in the last century or more; especially where a country allows too many parties to stand for election. This is another example of good intentions mutating to less good results; whole nations sleep-walking into a political system which is no longer fully democratic. Many voters are becoming more and more disenfranchised because of modern party politics with, in many cases, multiple parties vying for power. This is why people are rising up in demonstrations.

The above only leads to voter dissatisfaction and a greater tendency towards unrest. In such situations we can say that the regime of autocracy which has run Cuba for many decades has been more successful and consistent where the leaders have only the best intentions for the people of their country. We can only guess - but where wise kings are mentioned in the history (old testament) of the Jewish peoples that they were not democratically elected, but they did govern the people in a good and just manner. So the modern idea that democracy is the only way to govern has not always been the case in human history.

Good government can only come when those who govern are well educated in what it means to live by and administer truth, patience,

absence of anger in any form, non-stealing, freedom from fraud or deceit, forgiveness and tolerance - all those qualities which so-called Christians (and Europeans) are supposed to live by, if they follow the advice of the one they are supposed to believe in. This along with the recognition within the majority of the electorate (if elections are part of the government system) of the need for those good qualities to be part of the life of those they will vote for.

So bearing in mind the difficulties of democracy of a single nation not being able to be truly democratic. How do we expect the EU democracy of more than two dozen diverse nations to work at all?

The Birth of the European Union

The Treaty of Rome signed in 1957 by six European countries established two main ideas. Firstly the free movement of goods across their respective borders, to eventually become free of tariffs (import taxes). Secondly that they would all work towards a greater integration. It took several years for the tariffs to be completely removed. The greater integration would later include free movement of people, services and financial capital; not included in the Treaty of Rome. These three would require another treaty. There was no intention in 1957 to undermine the sovereignty of member countries or to create a European parliament. If this had been the case then Britain and other countries might not have joined the six in 1973. Yet as we have already seen the beginnings of such undermining begun in 1964 through a case law decision. Clearly British lawyers during 1969 to 1973 did not pick up on the significance of the 1964 case decision, where European law could take precedence. Hence mutation of the controls within the idea of European integration were creeping in; through the back door as it were. The Treaty of Rome did not aim at a political union within Europe. This means each member country was free to make regulations and laws to govern its own affairs without interference from other countries, unless such matters included the subject of trade across borders. It is important to be clear about this point; and to see later that the principle of 'no interference' was also abandoned by European law.

Here we need to look at the words used in the title "European Union" or the concept "United States of Europe"; and to focus on the words 'union' and 'united'. Both these terms imply a joining together

as one. The same idea is in the title "United States of America". The title itself presumes that some phenomenon has happened in the past which has brought all these states together as one. But this is clearly not true.

After the USA had achieved its independence from the UK in 1776 it still had internal troubles. The southern states were of a very different culture to those in the north. The south being mainly agricultural and the north mainly industrial. There were also ethnic differences. The civil war (1861 to 1864) was all about the southern states wanting independence. Yet they lost the war. Even so, as in Europe, after war ceased there were still elements within the continent as a whole which maintained their different views and cultures. Even today in the USA there are southerners who despise those in the north. So there is in reality no United States. This was a concept imposed on all the states by the will of politicians. There was no referendum to seek the will of the people in the USA. The same situation applies to Europe.

The main problem with using a title with the word "United" or "Union" in it, presumes that unity has been achieved. When the reality shows that this is not the case. Each state in the USA has very different laws and regulations to adjacent states; such that police are limited in chasing or seeking offenders in neighbouring states. Rules about voting and voting systems are different in each state. There is no 'union' in the ways that various states deal with human affairs. This means that integrated control in law becomes a complex and impossible task. United in name but not in deed is an illusion of culture, which leads to a false concept of a country or a group of countries. Also it takes away the energy of improving the situation of integration and more effective 'union'. The American dream is what it says - a dream - nothing more.

The Treaty of Rome 1958 did not give rise to a European Parliament, it was an unelected ad hoc committee of politicians. It was not until 1979 that elections were held to form the European Parliament; i.e. it became supposedly democratic. But Europe was still only dealing with economic issues those mainly of trade across its borders. The matters where movement of people, services and capital were involved had not yet been introduced. Hence another treaty was

required. As time passed the six and other countries that had joined the Common Market collaborated to make a new treaty embracing the previously intended aim of greater integration. This became known as the Maastricht Treaty and was finally ratified in 1992. This sparked off a series of referenda, in France, Denmark and Ireland. The French and Danish results were split more or less 50% - 50% over acceptance of the Treaty. The French slightly in favour and the Danish slightly against. So the European legislators had to go back to the drawing board to accommodate the Danish problems with the Treaty.

It is interesting to note, that the situation of 50 / 50 in France has not changed much since 1979. Even today the party of Marine le Penn, which opposes the EU and the Euro currency, is gaining ground over the ruling party. Europe is not a union - is it very fragile in some ways.

Areas of European Union Control and Controversy

There are currently around 27 treaties along with 15 conventions / sub-treaties in force which control the various matters of running and organising the European Union; governing 28 member countries or states. Many thousands of pages of text. This compares with only 7 articles along with amendments of the Constitution of the United states of America; only 21 pages long altogether - governing 50 states. The UK has no written constitution. All matters of government are run through a system of behavioural traditions. This allows tradition to change in accordance with new ways of doing things without the need for any legislation. It requires honesty and respect towards the customary ways.

The laws of the EU are passed in Brussels or Strasbourg and require each individual country to enact their own legislation for the implementation of the EU laws. This leads to a wide range of interpretation along with a wide range of policing or local control of the regulations. Here follows a few of the matters where laws now exist within the EU to control the running of the 28 states.

(1) National parliaments. (2) Court of Justice (3) Central banks (4) Investment banks. (5) Privileges and immunities (6) Human rights. (7) Structured co-operation. (8) Financial deficit (9) Convergence (10) The Euro currency. (11) Movement of people across borders (12) People outside the EU crossing EU borders (13) Asylum for EU

member citizens. (14) Services (15) Market competition (16) Economic cohesion. (17) Social cohesion (18) Territorial cohesion (19) Public broadcasting. (20) Imports (21) Exports (22) Trade tariffs (23) Agriculture (24) Fishing rights.

The above areas (and several others) extend into every facet of the lives of EU citizens; controlling matters which go far beyond the original desire to trade more easily with each other and work together. Such is the control, that all businesses have to expend effort and cost so as to be sure that they are not breaking EU regulations. Also individual citizens can never be sure that they are living legally by the laws originating within the EU. This is how a good idea has mutated into total control.

Such is the complexity and far reaching interference of EU legislation that many movements have arisen with the member countries which seek to either reform or undermine the EU as a whole. These groups are known within each country as 'Euro sceptics'. Although some countries prefer to use milder sounding names such as "EU reformers". These have all arisen due to the perception that the EU has undermined the national sovereignty of individual nations within the EU. These groups have failed to realise that the mutated direction of the EU is to remove the idea of individual national sovereignty and replace it with a single EU sovereignty. A form of totalitarian control. Maybe the Fourth Reich.

Other complaints are that the EU is too bureaucratic and lacks transparency (i.e. who is really controlling the EU). Many have complained that the individual citizen has been side-lined in favour of the commercial aspects of the EU - the same conflict which bedevils the running of the UK - that between the workers and the business leaders. The buzz words these days are GDP and 'the economy'. Subjects which many who speak about them do not really know what they are all about. As if these things are the only human issues which matter.

The Euro-scepticism, which exists in all 28 European member countries to one degree or another, has gradually grown such that in this current decade (i.e. survey in 2016) there are less than 50% of EU citizens who favour the EU continuing to control their lives. In 2016 Greece, the UK, France and Spain were all on the brink of breaking

from the EU. Britain was first to take the plunge and hold a referendum. Although all polls showed a win for those who wished to remain - the silent majority eventually won the day. Showing that free thinking people are against totalitarian control. The silent and little known mantra of the leavers was "Leave means liberation". Several other countries are waiting in the wings to see what happens. If the UK succeeds in leaving the EU and becomes a stronger country as a result - wait and see how many of those in the wings step forward and leave the EU. When they see that reform is not possible in such a way that the euro sceptics are happy, then leaving the EU will become the only option. It is really only a matter of time and the EU will either mutate into a form unrecognisable as legitimate government or it will disintegrate. Look at history - very few political systems which try to take total control have survived.

The Euro Currency Failure

Few people in the world understand that the value of money is a very fluid thing or even understand how it works at all. Let's imagine I want to sell my mobile phone. I have a price in mind, suppose it is £100 (100 UK pounds). This £100 to me is worth more than the mobile phone. If not I would keep the phone. For the person who decides to pay the £100 for it, the phone is worth more than the £100. Else they would not part with the money. So just like a fluid inside pipes, there needs to be a pressure difference for a flow to take place. So it is there needs to be a difference in value between the phone and the £100 in the minds of the traders, for there to be any movement of the money or the goods. This difference in value is the pressure which causes money or goods to flow. Yet both parties in the above theoretical transaction have given different values to both the phone and the £100. If it is properly understood, there are in reality four different values in the minds of the two parties involved in the transaction for there to be any trade at all.

This is what I mean by fluid and that most people do not understand how money works. This reality needs to be contemplated. More material for gaining cultural liberation.

It is mainly because of the US dollar that EU leaders imagined they could create a competitive currency idea. The US dollar gained its world wide status because the American bankers conned the world

into believing that the dollar was as stable as gold, and hence its equivalent. They convinced many countries to part with their gold and purchase dollars to put into their central banks in place of the gold. More need for Fort Knox in the USA. It is easier for the USA to print dollars than to mine gold.

Hence many world currencies became linked to the US dollar and world trade became dependent on exchange rates from each currency into the US dollar. Now most countries are using the US dollar as a means to price their goods and exchange them for currency around the world. This may require agreement or action from American central banks for that trade to happen where the US dollar is involved. The USA abuses this position when it wishes to subdue a political regime (e.g. Iran) by applying sanctions on those traders and countries worldwide who do not comply with the restrictive regime of the US against another regime.

When the ambitions of the EU leaders moved towards the idea of a United States of Europe, they saw that they might get a trading block which would compete with the USA. Hence they needed a currency which might eventually supplant the US dollar as a world trading currency. This was the undocumented driving force behind creating the Euro. This would free Europe from having to continually be a financial lap-dog of the USA. To get the strength as a global equivalent to the dollar, it would require all EU member states to give up their national currencies and to adopt the Euro instead. The German mark was the strongest currency in Europe before the Euro. This was the main strength behind the Euro. Without it there the Euro idea would have been a non-starter.

Prior to the emergence of the US dollar as a world wide currency, the UK pound sterling had been a world currency. It was trusted the world over and could be used almost anywhere for trade or commerce. Also we must not forget that there is a decade (or more) of UK GDP stashed away as UK pounds sterling, in the many UK off-shore tax havens; islands which are the remnants of the British Empire which did not ask for independence. Hence the UK saw no need to give up such a strong and trusted currency and to adopt the Euro. This decision encouraged other EU member countries to keep their own national currency. Hence the main concept of the Euro was thwarted

from the outset. Not predicted by the EU money wizards. Without the backing of the UK's global recognition for a trusted currency, the Euro had little chance of becoming a competitor to the US dollar.

Hence the Euro (€) has become more of a domestic currency than a world trading currency. But it has failed in some ways. The idea of a common currency which can be used across all EU member countries with the same value is a failure. Let us examine a few examples from the year 2018.

To purchase a flat in Greece outside a city centre would cost €1,262 per square meter. In Germany it would cost €3,293 per square meter; a factor of 2.61. The average net monthly earnings of a Greek person is €677. In Germany it is €2,196; a factor of 3.24. Although we can see that within each country the earnings related to flat purchase is not much different; what happens if a Greek wishes to purchase a flat in Germany or visa versa. Clearly the German has a great advantage when it comes to affordability. The same differences apply to hotel accommodation or flat rental. In Greece a monthly travel pass is €30 in Germany it is €70. So a Greek taking his Euros to travel in Germany would not get the same value for money. A restaurant meal for two in Greece is €30 in Germany it is €45. We can compare many prices between these two countries and find that a person going from one country to the other would either find things much cheaper or more expensive when using the same currency. The same can be found between any two European countries which have abandoned their national currency for the Euro. The money carries the same name but clearly not the same value. This difference in value cannot be addressed by any kind of exchange rate.

Although it is true that in the UK where naturally the same currency is used throughout, there are variations in earnings and costs. For example the average earnings in the south of England are around £600 per month whereas in the north they are around £550 per month; a factor of 1.1. House costs are about £200K in the north whereas in the south they are around £250K; a factor of 1.25. London and the South East of England have higher house prices but with correspondingly higher earnings. But the factors between areas in the UK are not as great as they are between Greece and Germany or those

between other countries which use the Euro in place of their previously independent currency.

What do we think the effect this has on trade outside the Euro-zone? For example when a Greek business person wishes to trade with non-European countries. How is the exchange value fixed when selling his goods abroad? The exchange value of the Euro with other world currencies is not fixed by the Greek banks, it is fixed by the European Central Bank. Hence it becomes impossible for Greeks to determine an exchange rate which is different from the rest of Europe. When the Greeks had their own drachma they were free to negotiate foreign trade rates and hence to facilitate profitable trade with other countries. Now they cannot. It should not be a surprise that the Greek economy has suffered so much since they switched to the Euro. Also they clearly cannot afford to buy and sell items between other European countries like Germany and to make a profit. When the Greeks had drachmas and the Germans had marks, crossing from one country to another would involve an exchange rate between currencies. Now there is a need for the Greeks to get an exchange rate for their Greek-Euros so that they could get a fair deal in Germany with German-Euros. But because the currency is considered to be the same they cannot get value for money. The Euro has created this discrepancy between EU nations which could otherwise be addressed if they each retained their own currencies.

In my limited view the Euro is a failure both as a world currency and a domestic currency. Another good intention gone bad.

The Idea of a European Army

Both Germany and France have promoted the idea that the EU should develop its own army. This is a great mutation of the original desire to simply trade more effectively with each other in Europe. Now we see in this idea the rebirth of the souls who once saw the need for military controls in Europe. Once again we have what seems a good idea and perhaps quite harmless for the population of the EU; and maybe seen as beneficial. But taking the theme of mutation contained within this paper, which cannot be denied has happened, we must be sure the use of such an army will not be limited to external threats.

I have already mentioned the Neo-Nazi groups which have arisen within many countries in the EU itself. These could eventually be seen as an internal threat to the stability of Europe. Many nations across the world have called in their own army to quell internal uprisings. So the EU would not be setting a precedent if it decided to quell a Neo-Nazi uprising, however small, with the use of the future EU army. Don't believe it could never happen. And let us not limit the term "uprising" to Neo-Nazis.

This century has seen many huge demonstrations by populist movements within the EU. These could also be seen as an internal threat. Incidentally the term populist is a misnomer, it is the governing politicians and the media who have used this term to try and discount what is really the will of the people; which really means it is the true face of democracy. But they have tried to pass it off under the term 'populist' as if it may be an insignificant view of a few people.

The Dutch Prime Minister has rightly called the EU army idea, "A step too far." To which I agree whole heartily. I have used the term "Liberation" at the beginning of this paper in terms of freedom from culturally limiting ideas. Also it was used in respect of the outcome of Brexit as "Leave means liberation". If Brexit is successful, which I see as a possibility, the UK could become liberated from the EU and from the possible huge cost of having to pay towards the creation of an EU army. I sense that if the army idea becomes firmed up, then it will not only be 'a step too far' but the last straw for many anti-EU groups across Europe. This will then sound the death knell for the European experiment. But if those anti-EU groups rise up in demonstration, will they be seen as an internal threat? The fanatic politicians of the Fourth Reich will not tolerate dissent from their ambitions for the United States of Europe. The threat of "hell" has already been made by the president of the EU towards harmless UK politicians who are against the EU experiment.

The very first EU citizen that is killed by its own army will see the commencement of the Fourth Reich. Repeating the event of the many deaths perpetrated by the First Reich the HRE, when those who opposed the teaching, now known to be false, of the Roman Catholic church, were killed by their own fellow Christians. In the Third Reich

it was not only Jews who were victims of Hitler's regime. Apart from the Jews there were altogether nearly another eight million people exterminated. This included Hungarian Romas, disabled Germans, Jehovah's witnesses, Polish & Slavic peoples, communists (Russians), socialists and homosexuals, were among those targeted. For many of those groups their children were also slaughtered. It is clear from that list that there was a strong element of fanatic 'so called' Christian doctrine behind the Nazi holocaust. People killing fellow citizens - this is murder.

If the EU army is used against its own citizens, the above history will repeat itself. The sooner Europe reverts to nations who have control of their own borders, their own currency exchange rates and who (or who not) is allowed to enter their own country, the sooner we can avert the possibility of this Fourth Reich becoming a reality. The more Europe moves towards "greater integration" the more there is a risk of the Fourth Reich becoming a real possibility. All free thinking people who are citizens of Europe must resist further moves to eliminate the sovereign states that have existed in Europe for many centuries. The EU idea is not yet a hundred years in the making, far from it. It has gone far enough. We should all seek to avert further integration of the individual European states.

Conclusion

The main subject contained within this paper is for readers to make a concerted attempt to understand how politicians can be so bad at their job. This means understanding that they are ordinary people cast into a role which has an effect on many other people, but that this does not make them better at being able to overcome their entrenched habitual psychology. In order to understand this facet of human life we need to have embraced the mysterious subject of karma and how it works. And to understand karma we need to make an attempt to see it working within our own lives.

The human being is clearly much more than a physical body governed only by genes and chemistry. This is the mysterious side of this subject which, sadly and perhaps unfortunately, very few people decide to delve into. A car mechanic does not attempt to fix a broken down motor car unless he first has knowledge of how it works. Gaining this knowledge may take him some time and need much practical application. So why do we think we can fix broken politics if we do not understand how it works. And to fully understand how it works we need to make some attempt to understand how the functioning parts within it work. This means - how does the human being work.

It is not essential to believe in rebirth of the human soul, or that a human being has a soul; or even belief in karma. If these things are not understood in the way portrayed in this paper, then the reader must do their own research and come up with an equally sustainable understanding of how human life works, especially where habits and entrenched behaviour controls our lives.

By sustainable I mean a system of knowledge which can stand for many thousands of years and be proved to work by the many first hand witness accounts of it. This especially where karma is concerned. The knowledge of karma put forward in this paper is not a mere passing fancy or a fashion of thought. It has been based on first hand verification of it including teaching and knowledge of a handed down system of understanding which no western university can come anywhere near in its practical application.

So readers may decide to take the short cut and instead of trying to develop their own system, instead to take what is written here as being

the most readily acceptable knowledge of how the current system of political controls through out the world have appeared in the way we see them.

The only way to understand how political leaders do not seem to learn from history and to avoid the pitfalls which many previous systems have encountered, is to include an understanding of karma. This means history repeats itself many times through the agency of entrenched habits re-appearing within new born human beings.

The Romans were appallingly barbaric. They punished ordinary offenders and dissenters by crucifying them. They also had an arena where citizens sat and watched as prisoners were made to face lions and other wild animals who were very hungry. This barbaric behaviour became reborn into the so called Christian leaders of the Roman Catholic church. But it took a different form, that of burning at the stake people who were follower of their own idea of religion. Later this became reborn as the atrocious way in which Hitler killed more than thirteen million people in Europe. Many of whom were citizens of his own country or followers of the same belief system which he followed.

Europeans have spread this behaviour across the world by having migrated to many countries and installed themselves there by subduing the indigenous people of those countries. Many of the European entrenched barbaric habits have been demonstrated in the many countries which were once colonies of the Europeans.

Now we see the same thing gradually being reborn within the ways that the European Union is mutating. But it is reborn in a different way using the same basic driving psychology; that which seeks to control the lives of others. Whatever the methods we see throughout history we should see them simply as the many manifestations of seeking to take control. This way of seeing it and understanding it will make it much clearer to the reader who has the desire to become free from the cultural conditioning which may have hitherto clouded an understanding of what is really happening.

I rest my case.

APPENDIX ONE

Taken from the paper called "Did Jesus Study Vedanta".

EUROCENTRICISM

So that this paper can be more truly appreciated I wish to introduce readers to a concept which I will call **Eurocentricism**. This is maybe a new word for many, so I need to explain what is meant by it. In my other papers readers will see that, although I was born and educated in England (UK), I have travelled and absorbed the ancient culture of non-European peoples; viz. Pythagorean Sufism and Indian philosophy. This travel to far away countries was not for academic reasons, but for personal interest in the culture of those places visited. Also I went to those places to study under accomplished masters of the various subjects that I was deeply interested in. Hence in my papers there has been an awakening of this subject of Eurocentricism; meaning that these countries have suffered from impositions which have been introduced or forced onto their culture from European type people and mentioned to me by those masters when teaching me. This information I have dutifully passed on in my other papers.

In my view much of this whole world has become subjected to ideas coming from people who have originated from Europe. So much of the whole world is now suffering from Eurocentricism. These Europeans began their promulgation during times when a fanatic false form of Christianity was gripping them. Hence their fanatic false ideas of their belief system were forced onto other cultures. Later, many of these European countries have given up their fanatic approach to their beliefs; but unfortunately the damage is done, and those other countries, worldwide, are still suffering the effects and have hung on to the fanaticism.

In subsequent centuries this has been followed with the Eurocentric dominance of scientific theories, many of which are also false, in that the unproved theories are taught in schools as if they are fact. Add to this the highly mutable nature of digital ways of living and it now it looks like the world will be ruined due to these things spreading into the lives of all people; taking away their freedom to think and act for themselves in line with their traditional cultures; and giving them weapons and other technology which they never could have produced

themselves. Let alone the criminal and other harmful activities through digital means, which they could not have easily derived by themselves.

Yet if we go back to the times when Jesus was living on this planet, Britain was nothing, America was nothing and most of Europe was troubled with barbaric, generally uncivilised, tribes of people beating the brains out of each other, stealing each others valuables and women. These European people, who gradually became more organised and a little more civilised, achieved this due to a few good ideas which were spoken by Jesus. A tiny fraction of his knowledge and philosophy changed a whole continent. Where did Jesus learn to speak in such a way? Few people who have belonged to fanatic religious sects have asked this question. If they had really understood Jesus' teachings they would have dropped their centuries old primitive habit of wanting to make or tell other people (or nations) how to live their lives, now called Eurocentricism.

It is not yet a century since Europeans stopped fighting each other. Yet they have not stopped trying to impose their ideas onto other nations. This imposition is coming from all those types whose ancestry originates in Europe, which ever continent they currently live on. They brought the habit, of telling others what to do, with them to their country and have never stopped it nor have they controlled it; or even realised that it is there. This is what I mean by global Eurocentricism. Europeans do not realise what they have been responsible for.

However, more than two thousand years before Jesus' time there was high civilisation in both China and India. These areas were the centre of the world in terms of technology and knowledge of how to live a noble life. Yet then as now these cultures do not have the habit of telling other cultures how to live their lives. Before Jesus' time middle eastern peoples looked further East for trade, trinkets, teaching and technology. In the city of Taxila (near the modern Afghan - Pakistan border) there was a university which taught all subjects to a high degree. The Harappan civilisation in the Indus valley had architecturally planned cities with organised streets, and drainage systems. They had a sophisticated waste disposal system. Each house had a proper toilet and bathing room. The sewage went through a

system of drains getting bigger as they collected the waste to convey it onto agricultural fields for fertilisation. They made building bricks with amazing accuracy and had many technologies relating to pottery, metal smelting, fine jewellery and other manufacturing techniques. All these along with a sophisticated weights and measures system.

All this advancement thousands of years before Europeans and peoples of the Middle East started to become civilised. Other evidence shows that the Harappans of the Indus valley were also living by the ancient knowledge of the Vedas and much of the culture they had then has continued into the present day.³ Their knowledge and ways have survived thousands of years, without the need to tell anyone that they must also live by it; and much longer lasting than this temporary destructive digital electronic fashion might be.

It was into the area of the Indus valley that Jesus went to find a connection with that ancient teaching. Contrary to the way Eurocentricism has promoted his teaching, it did in fact come from the Indus valley and associated areas. A land where the people of Jesus' time knew to go to get more advanced things which they were not capable of producing. It was where he learned to understand human psychology and how to avoid, or progress beyond, the need to force people or tell them how they must live their lives. Instead he showed the options available and left people to choose the appropriate way for themselves. Hold the above in mind as you read the rest of this paper. It may change your view of the old Eurocentric story told about Jesus, his life and teachings.

And you may consider that old Eurocentric view to now be obsolete.

³ The Harappan Civilization by Tarini Carr - Archaeology Online